

18.11.2021

Newsletter

 COREnect

COREnect' White Paper is out!

We are excited to announce the release of COREnect's White Paper!

→ "Passive user or innovative driver? Europe's future role in microelectronics and connectivity"

[Download the White Paper!](#)

COREnect's booth at EF ECS

EF ECS 2021 will take place online! COREnect will participate with a booth. Visit us! 23-25 November 2021.

[EF ECS](#)

Interview with Yanning Zou!

The Technische Universität Dresden (TUD) is the project coordinator and one of the largest "Technische Universitäten" in Germany.

[READ](#)

3rd COREnect Workshop!

The 3rd COREnect Workshop will take place on the 1st of February 2022. Stay tuned to the COREnect website and social media channels for more details in the upcoming months!

COREnect
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